

INITIAL EVALUATION OF COMMERCIALY AVAILABLE InGaAsP DFB LASER DIODES FOR USE IN HIGH-SPEED DIGITAL FIBER OPTIC TRANSCEIVERS

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ABSTRACT

NASA has been pursuing the development of high-speed fiber-optic transceivers for use in a number of Space Data System Applications. Prior joint development programs with the Air Force/Rome Air Development Center have developed a family of military-qualified transceivers operating below 50 Mbits/sec. Current efforts are pointed toward a high-performance all-integrated-circuit transceiver operating up to the 3-5 Gbits/sec range. This paper presents details of the evaluation and selection of candidate high-speed optical sources to be used in the new space-qualified high-performance transceiver.

INTRODUCTION

InGaAsP distributed feedback (DFB) laser diodes offer the potential for providing a high-quality optical source for use in single-mode fiber-optic data systems. A DFB laser of this type is to be incorporated with the high-performance electronics package for the fiber-optic transceiver. For these applications, the DFB laser should operate single mode, provide 1-5 milliwatts of optical power output, and be capable of modulation in the Gbits/sec range. In addition, the device should have stable and long-life emission properties. This paper presents data on the performance of commercially-available DFB lasers and discusses their performance relative to each other and to their structural design with regard to their use in high-performance fiber-optic transceivers.

The DFB lasers were obtained from seven commercial manufacturers. A previous report contains detailed information on the CW operating characteristics of the laser diodes.¹ Tables 1 and 2 give a summary of these CW performance characteristics. The data taken on each laser included threshold current, differential quantum efficiency, CW side mode suppression ratio, wavelength temperature coefficient, threshold temperature coefficient, natural linewidth, and far field pattern. We found that laser diodes with buried heterostructures and first-order gratings had, in general, the best CW operating characteristics.

The main thrust of this paper concentrates on the modulated characteristics of the DFB laser diodes. Modulated linewidth, modulated side mode

suppression ratio, and frequency response are mainly of interest.

BACKGROUND

When selecting a laser diode for a high-speed fiber-optic transceiver, one must consider several of the laser's operating characteristics. These characteristics are discussed below.

Since the laser is to be incorporated into an all-integrated-circuit transmitter, the threshold current must be low and the efficiency must be high due to current driving limitations imposed by the laser driver integrated circuits (ICs). A survey of six commercially available laser driver ICs shows maximum bias current capabilities of 40-80 mA and maximum modulation current capabilities of 30-80 mA. The highest threshold current reported here is 39 mA, which is just at the bias limit of two of the laser driver ICs. The modulation currents vary from 8.9 mA to 34.9 mA, depending on the laser and the operating power. Hence, we see that some of the lasers could not be used with certain laser drivers. This fact is important if the best performing laser driver ICs have the lowest current driving limitations. Performance comparisons of the laser driver ICs are currently being done.

Frequency response of the laser diode must also be considered. For example, a laser diode with a frequency response of 2 GHz is not very useful in a transceiver designed for the 3-5 GHz range. A study of the manufacturer's specified rise and fall times of the laser diode and a study of the structure of the laser can give a good indication of its bandwidth. The important concept here is that a laser with otherwise good overall characteristics could be eliminated as a candidate because of its relatively slow modulation capabilities.

Side mode suppression ratio (SMSR) is another important characteristic to be considered. The chance of bit errors occurring in a fiber optic transceiver system increases as the SMSR gets smaller. This is mainly due to the increased chance of mode partition noise occurring between the main mode and the nearest side mode. The effects of mode partition noise can be seen as a bit error rate (BER) floor when plotting BER vs. received optical power.^{2,3} Although

the CW SMSR is a good indication of the performance of a laser diode, the modulated SMSR gives a better indication of the performance of the laser in a real system. Therefore, a laser which has a good CW SMSR which drastically degrades when modulated could not be considered as a viable source for a high-speed transceiver.

When a laser diode is directly modulated with injection current, its spectral linewidth tends to broaden, or chirp. Spectral chirp can have adverse effects on a system when combined with the effects of wavelength, or chromatic, dispersion of optical fibers. Wavelength dispersion in an optical fiber occurs as a result of the different propagation speeds of different wavelengths of light as they travel down the fiber. The main result of this dispersion can be seen by the broadening of an optical pulse as it travels down the length of an optical fiber, with the amount of pulse broadening increasing as the spectral width of the optical source increases. The amount of pulse broadening also depends on the length of the optical fiber and the characteristic chromatic dispersion value of the fiber.

As an example of fiber dispersion, consider a .5 nanosecond wide optical pulse with a spectral width of .8 nanometers which is sent down 20 km of fiber that has 15 ps/km/nm chromatic dispersion. The width of the optical pulse exiting the fiber would be broadened by 240 picoseconds, or .24 nanoseconds. Thus, the original .5 ns wide input pulse would exit the fiber being .74 ns wide. This would result in pulses overlapping, or aliasing, in multi-gigabit systems. Since the amount of pulse broadening partially depends on the spectral width of the optical source, it is desirable to have a very spectrally narrow source. As mentioned before, laser diodes tend to spectrally broaden when they are modulated. Therefore, we have measured the modulated linewidth of each of the lasers at high-modulation rates.

EXPERIMENTAL

Laser diode current modulation circuitry was built using a commercial laser driver integrated circuit (LDIC). A printed circuit board with high-speed capabilities was built to accommodate the LDIC. The laser driver had a specified 3 dB bandwidth of 3 GHz. The measured 3 dB bandwidth of the laser driver was 6 GHz with a resistive load. However, due to limitations in driver-to-laser interconnections, the useful frequency response of the driver/laser combination was limited to about 2 GHz. Presently under development are driver/laser packages that will modulate the laser in the 3-5 GHz range; however, the data given in this report are for modulation frequencies of 2 GHz and less.

TEST RESULTS

The results given in the remainder of this report are given for laser diode optical output powers of 3 mW, unless otherwise noted. Modulation tests are performed at 50 percent duty cycle with the laser biased at threshold.

Side Mode Suppression Ratio

The SMSR results from the modulated time-averaged spectra for eight DFB lasers are shown in graphical form in Figure 1. As expected, the SMSR decreased as the modulation frequency increased. It can be seen that the modulated SMSR at 2 GHz varied among the lasers from 8 dB to 37.7 dB.

Modulated Linewidth

The linewidth results from the modulated time-averaged spectra are shown in Figures 2 and 3. Figure 2 shows the 3 dB linewidth and Figure 3 shows the 20 dB linewidth. As expected, the linewidth increases with increasing modulation rate. Even though there was a fair spread of modulated linewidth values (.95 Å to 6.1 Å at 3 dB, 2 GHz; 6.7 Å to 11.3 Å at 20 dB, 2 GHz), there were no drastic differences in modulated linewidth among the lasers. Actual operation of the laser diodes in a fiber optic transceiver may be needed to determine the effects of such an evenly spaced range of values of modulated linewidth.

Frequency Response

Although the frequency response of the laser diodes has not yet been experimentally determined, good estimations can be made. Of the lasers tested here, the manufacturer's specified rise and fall times indicated modulation capabilities ranging from 2 GHz to 6.6 GHz. And as expected, the lasers with special capacitance-reducing structures had the highest specified frequency response, while the remaining lasers had the lowest specified frequency response.

SUMMARY/CONCLUSIONS

When considering the major CW and modulated characteristics of the DFB laser diodes, 2 lasers (lasers #5 and #6) stand out as performing good in every category. Laser #1 had a relatively large threshold current of 29.6 mA and a fairly small CW SMSR of 33 dB, which decreased even farther to 26 dB at 2 GHz modulation. Laser #2 had a low threshold current and high efficiency. It even had a good CW SMSR of 38 dB, but the SMSR degraded to 22 dB when modulated at 2 GHz. Laser #3 had good CW characteristics but only had a manufacturer-specified bandwidth of 2 GHz. This specification is also supported by its structure which suggests relatively large junction capacitances. Laser #5 had a low threshold, good efficiency, large CW SMSR (43 dB), large modulated SMSR (37 dB at 2 GHz), and a good far

field pattern (26 x 33 degrees). Laser #6 had a reasonable threshold current (25 mA), good efficiency, large CW SMSR (41 dB), large modulated SMSR (38 dB at 2 GHz), and a good far field pattern (30 x 32 degrees). Laser #7 had a good SMSR both CW (44 dB) and modulated (35.5 dB at 2 GHz) but had a large threshold current (38.9 mA) and a low efficiency. It also had the most elliptical beam pattern (23 x 53 degrees).

We conclude that laser #5 and laser #6 would be good candidates for further evaluation for use in the high-performance space-qualified fiber-optic transceiver. Laser #5 was a buried heterostructure laser with a first-order grating and 2 percent/80 percent facet reflectivities. Laser #6 was a buried heterostructure laser with a phase-shifted first-order grating and 1 percent facet reflectivities. (An interesting note here is that a previous report concludes that phase-shifted DFBs are superior to conventional ones in optical fiber transmission performance with optical feedback⁴). Further evaluation would involve testing at higher modulation rates, determination of the actual frequency response of the lasers, and evaluation of the lasers in a real fiber optic system to determine the actual effect of laser chirping on performance.

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TABLE 1
DISTRIBUTED FEEDBACK (DFB) LASER DIODE
CW CHARACTERISTICS SUMMARY

LASER	Threshold Current (mA)	Operating Current (mA)			Efficiency (mW/mA)	dIth/dT (mA/°C)	Far Field (degrees)	
		1mW	3mW	5mW			θ_x	θ_y
1A	32.1	35.5	45.2	55.5	0.20	0.70	34	52
1B	29.6	35.4	44.9	56.0	0.18	0.65	35	47
2	14.1	16.4	23.3	30.0	0.30	0.25	34	37
3	16.8	21.7	35.8	48.5	0.15	0.31	38	40
4	10.6	14.9	29.1	42.8	0.14	0.20	36	a
5A	10.0	13.4	23.9	33.7	0.20	0.23	34	44
5B	15.0	18.5	26.6	34.6	0.25	0.31	26	33
6A	20.1	25.4	39.5	51.7	0.15	0.32	—	—
6B	25.4	30.0	39.3	48.5	0.21	0.40	30	32
7A	36.7	44.6	64.3	79.3	0.12	0.71	—	—
7B	38.9	46.3	60.6	73.8	0.14	0.65	23	53

- o All tests at 25°C unless otherwise noted
- o dIth/dT refers to threshold tempco over a 20-30°C range
- o a - Unable to test θ_x due to laser's submount geometry
- o Efficiency measured from front facet

TABLE 2
DISTRIBUTED FEEDBACK (DFB) LASER DIODE
SPECTRAL CHARACTERISTICS SUMMARY

LASER	SMSR* (dB)			LINEWIDTH (MHz)		MODULATION (100MHz - 1GHz)	Wavelength Tempco (nm/°C)
	1mW	3mW	5mW	3mW	5mW		
1A	-28	-36	-39	60	40	—	—
1B	-27	-33	-34	75	45	—	0.0700
2	-33	-40	-42	70	55	line broadening	0.0975
3	-36	-41	-43	65	50	line broadening	0.0933
4	-27	-34	-35	a	a	modes above -27dB	0.0908
5A	-38	-44	-46	60	40	line broadening	0.0842
5B	-39	-41	-42	35	25	—	0.0920
6A	-42	-44	-45	65	55	—	0.0893
6B	—	—	—	75	60	—	0.0900
7A	—	—	—	a	a	—	0.0830
7B	-38	-44	-45	60	35	—	0.0873

- o All tests at 25°C unless otherwise noted
- o Wavelength tempco measured over a 20-30°C range
- o Linewidth measured under CW conditions
- o * refers to Side Mode Suppression Ratio
- o a - Lasers showed an unusually large linewidth

FIGURE 1
MODULATED SIDE MODE SUPPRESSION RATIO

FIGURE 2
3 dB MODULATED LINEWIDTH

FIGURE 3
20 dB MODULATED LINEWIDTH

